

Analysis of the Effect of Communication, Competence and Work Discipline on Job Satisfaction at PT. Tribahtera Srikandi

Lila Maria Kaban¹, Yusuf Ronny Edward²

¹Universitas Pelita Harapan, Indonesia

²Universitas Prima Indonesia, Indonesia

Corresponding Author: Lila Maria Kaban

ABSTRACT

This study aims to determine the effect of communication, competence and work discipline on job satisfaction at PT. Tribahtera Srikandi. This research was conducted at PT. Tribahtera Srikandi lasted for 6 months, starting from January 2020 to June 2020. Sampling was taken in research using proportional random sampling method. The population in this study are all employees of factory workers in PT. Tribahtera Srikandi 155 people. The number of respondents in this study was established by using the statistics of the population, amounting to 112 people. The instruments used to collect data are questionnaires from communication, competence, work discipline and job satisfaction. The data analysis tool in this study is a multiple linear regression by carrying out a classic assumption test that is continued by testing the partial hypothesis or t test, the simultaneous hypothesis test or the F test, and the calculation of the coefficient of determination. The contribution of communication, competence and work discipline variables explained the variable of job satisfaction as big as 0.765 or 76.5%. The remaining 0.235 or 23.5% was influenced by other independent variables not examined in this study.

Keywords: Communication, Competence, Work Discipline, Job Satisfaction

INTRODUCTION

Marine class is one of the agricultural commodities that has a role in the Indonesian economy. Indonesia as one

of the world's biggest producers of marriages, so that the commitment of foreign exchange earners is very important to the nation of Indonesia. In addition, it is also a library of works that can provide income for many people.

With the existence of gardeners and palm oil farmers in the area, slowly but slowly the economy builds the area around it. The most obvious impact is to become a locomotive of rural economic development. Other impacts can also be said to be the industry that absorbs the most labor, encourages GDP growth and reduces poverty in Indonesia.

One of the challenges in the maritime industry is to improve the quality of human resources (HR) by having qualified human resources who are able to work effectively and efficiently to improve engineering at both the regional and international level.

PT. Tribahtera Srikandi a company engaged in the field of plantations and palm oil factories that are located in the village of Tandike, Subdistrict of Baek, Regency of Mandailing Natal, North Sumatra Province, processing the fruits of the people around and in the fields of agriculture having succeeded in providing welfare to residents of the district of Padang.

The development and growth of PT. Tribahtera Srikandi sustained by its human resources (HR). Job satisfaction is an important factor that determines the seriousness of employees in carrying out

their work so that the organization's mission and mission can be achieved. The high level of over-employee turnover is one of the reflections on the satisfaction of the workforce and is the challenge that PT Tribahtera Srikandi is currently facing, even though it has an impact on the achievement of overall production results.

The following is the employee overturn data at PT. Tribahtera Srikandi as follows:

Table 1. Employee Turnover

Year	Semester	% Employee Turnover
2018	I (January – June)	20
	II (July – December)	21
2019	I (January – June)	25
	II (July – December)	30

Source: PT. Tribahtera Srikandi, 2020

One factor that influences job satisfaction is communication. Good communication between employees and leaders of other employees and employees will increase job satisfaction (Rizal, 2015). Another factor that can influence job satisfaction is competency. Competence has a positive and significant effect on increasing employee satisfaction (Ronny and Calen, 2019). Apart from the discipline of work is also one of the factors that can influence the low level of employee satisfaction in working in an organization (Dany et. al., 2017).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Communication

Communication or communication originates from the original language, which means notification or exchange (Wiryanto, 2004:5). Communication is an attempt to convey a message to other parties, so that there is a transfer and exchange of information from a communication to a communication.

The indications of communication according to Purwanto (2011) are as follows:

1.Perception

An intelligent communicator should be able to predict whether the messages he will deliver will be received by the communicant or not.

2.Accuracy

In general, the audience has a clear mindset. In order for communication to reach the target, someone needs to express something in accordance with what is in their thinking framework.

3.Credibility

In communicating, communicators need to have a high degree of confidence and optimism that the audience is trustworthy.

4.Control

In communicating, the audience will give a reaction or response to the message conveyed. Reaction can make a person laugh, cry, act, change thoughts, or be gentle.

5.Harmony

A good communicator will always be able to maintain a good friendship relationship with the audience so that the communication can run smoothly and achieve its goals.

Competence

According to Spencer & Spencer (Moehariono, 2009), stating that competence is an underlying characteristic of a person is related to the effectiveness of individual performance in his work or the characteristics of the performance of the performance of individuals who have a relationship between the cause and effect of the criteria that are referred to, effective or superior performance in certain situations.

According to Davis and Newstrom (2009) states that, competency is a capability perspective and people knowledge, especially to the impact on ability for need in business via minimizing costs and optimizing services to customers for more for less.

The indications of competition according to Gordon (Sutrisno 2013) are as follows:

1.Knowledge, which is conscious and in cognitive terms.

2.Understanding, that is in cognitive and affective possessed by individuals.

3.Value, that is the standard of behavior that has been believed and as far as the psychologist has become known in someone.

4.Ability, which is something that is owned by individuals to carry out the duties or work that is assigned to the workforce.

5.Attitude, that is feeling (happy-not-happy, like-disliked) or acted out against the people who come from outside.

6.Interest, which is the tendency of someone to do something.

Work Discipline

According to Sutrisno (2013), discipline is an attitude of willingness and willingness to obey and adhere to the norms that apply around it. Good employee discipline will accelerate corporate goals, while degenerative discipline will obstruct barriers and slow down the achievement of company goals.

According to Terry in Sutrisno (2013), discipline is a means of moving employees, so that every work can run smoothly, should it be endeavored so that there is good discipline.

The dimensions used in assessing the work discipline of each employee from each company difference, Handoko (2001) states the dimensions used to assess disciplinary performance (1)attendance, (2)observance, (3)timeliness and (4)behavior.

Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction is the level of feeling someone does in a job. The attitude is based on perceptions about work or environmental work, that perception is the cognitive process (meaning giving) used by someone to interpret and understand the views of individuals in seeing things the same way differently.

According to Robbins (2008), job satisfaction is a general attitude to one's work; the difference between the number of rewards received by workers and the amount of rewards that they believe is accepted. Job satisfaction is also a feeling posited about an occupation which is the result of valuation from some characteristics.

According to Luthans (2011), satisfaction of workmanship is a positive feeling that is formed from the assessment of the work of the employees in their work based on the perception of the workforce as well as the work, which means that what is gained in the work is fulfilling what is considered important.

Luthans (2011) explains that there are five indications of working satisfaction that:

1.The work itself. In this workmanship provides interesting assignments, opportunities for learning, and opportunities to assume responsibility.

2.Salary. The amount of wages received and the level of maturity can be compared to what is assumed to be compared to others in the organization.

3.Promotion. Opportunities for work in organizations. Chromosome opportunities have different effects on job satisfaction, because the chromosomes have a number of different forms and have various awards.

4.Coworkers. The degree to which partners work if they are technical and social support. Work groups act as sources of support, comfort, advice and assistance to individual members.

5.Supervision. Ability to provide technical assistance and behavioral support. At present, there is an increasing level of oversight that influences job satisfaction, which is centered on employees by using personal interest and caring for employees. The other dimension is participation in decision making that influences their needs.

Effect of Communication on Job Satisfaction

Communication is one of the important factors in the continuation of activities in the life of an organization. Good communication smoothness strongly supports all employees in carrying out and completing their duties will affect the achievement of the objectives of the company.

According to Rizal (2015) in his research, communication shows a positive

and significant effect on job satisfaction in communication which is directed clearly by the leadership of employee satisfaction.

Effect of Competence on Job Satisfaction

According to Iswahyu (2014) competence is the ability to carry out the tasks according to the film of knowledge and skills in technology and experience that is relevant to the field of assignment so that it can develop the motivation of the work concerned and the improvement of its work.

According to Nurfatmala (2016) in her research, it shows that competence has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction. High job satisfaction is supported by competencies owned by employees as well as special expertise owned by the company. With a lot of competence, employees work together more comfortably in work, feel the maximum contribution and effort for the success of the organization and performance of individuals and groups.

According to Saputra, et. al. (2018) in his study showed that competence has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction.

Effect of Work Discipline on Job Satisfaction

Discipline is one of the supporting factors in achieving job satisfaction. Employees have a good work discipline will be reflected from the attitude of honest employees in carrying out the duties,

responsible to their respective jobs, work according to the time determined by the company, present at a timely time, follow the procedures work and be able to use the complete workmanship quickly. According to Rivai (2004), work discipline is a tool used by managers to communicate with employees and to the prevailing social norms.

According to Dany, et. al., (2017) in his research, it shows that the work discipline has a significant positive effect on job satisfaction, high performance, and high discipline work performance.

RESEARCH METHODS

This research was conducted at PT. Tribahtera Srikandi is located in the village of Tangerang, District of Balea, Regency of Mandailing Natal - North Sumatra. This type of research is associative quantitative research. According to Sugiyono (2014) the definition of a quantitative associative research method is research that aims to determine the effect or also the relationship between two or more variables.

In this study, associative research methods are used to determine the magnitude of the influence between one variable with another variable. The population in this study is all employees at PT. Tribahtera Srikandi 155 employees. Samples were taken based on the probability sampling technique that is proportionate random sampling using the formula oflovin so that there were up to 112 employees.

The research model is as follows:

Figure 1. Research Model

The research was carried out at a certain time (cross sectional in nature) that reflected the phenomenon of a situation in a year 2020. The scale of the variable measurement used in this study was a Likert scale. To test the model and hypothesis used in multiple linear regression analysis, this research uses SPSS version 24, hypothesis testing is conducted through t test and F test.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

PT. Tribahtera Srikandi is a company engaged in the field of maritime plants which were established in 2012, and is based in the village of Tandikek, the district of Batak, district of Mandailing Natal - North Sumatra. PT. Tribahtera Srikandi a company that actively manages the farming community in the sub-district of Roanto Baek which is incorporated in the village unit cooperatives (KUD) so that fresh and processed fruits are the fruits of the surrounding community. With this, the existence of PT. Tribahtera Srikandi brought an impact on the economic growth and welfare of the community in the district of ofanto Baek.

Before testing the hypothesis using the t test and F test, a classic assumption test was carried out which consisted of a normality test, a multicollinearity test and a hesteroscedasticity test.

The results of the classic assumption test are as follows:

1. Nominality Test

Normality test with the Kolmogrov Smirnov method according to Priyatno (2014), the testing criteria are:

a.If the significance value is >0.05 , then the data is normally distributed.

b.If the significance value is <0.05 , then the data are not normally distributed

Table 2. Normality Test

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test		
		Unstandardized Residual
N		112
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	.0000000
	Std. Deviation	1.66601911
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.081
	Positive	.065
	Negative	-.081
Test Statistic		.081
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.065 ^c
a. Test distribution is Normal.		
b. Calculated from data.		
c. Lilliefors Significance Correction.		

The table above shows the Asymp value. sig is 0.065, the value indicates that the value is more than 0.05, so that it can be concluded that the data has fulfilled the normal distribution of residual data requirements.

2. Multicollinearity Test

Multicollinearity can also be seen from (1) tolerance value and its opponents, (2) variance inflation factor (VIF). Tolerance measures the chosen variability of the selected independent variables that are not explained by the other independent variables. So the value of tolerance is low with a high VIF value (because $VIF=1/tolerance$). A common cut-off value used to indicate multicollinearity is a tolerance value less than 0.10 or with a VIF value greater than 10 (Ghozali, 2016).

Table 3. Multicollinearity Test

Coefficients ^a								
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	-1.304	1.364		-.956	.341		
	X ₁	.375	.054	.423	6.939	.000	.569	1.759
	X ₂	.191	.051	.189	3.744	.000	.834	1.199
	X ₃	.435	.058	.448	7.552	.000	.600	1.665

a. Dependent Variable: Y

The results of multicollinearity testing can be known as VIF value and

tolerance as follows: The communication variable has a VIF value of 1.759 and

tolerance of 0.569. The competency variable has a VIF value of 1.199 and a tolerance of 0.834. The working discipline variable has a VIF value of 1.665 and a tolerance of 0.600. Of the conditions stated that VIF value <10 and tolerance >0.10, the mean of the variable depth of multicollinearity and the values obtained from the calculation are in accordance with the determination of the value of VIF and tolerance, then it can be

concluded that the variability of the dependent variable and the values obtained from the calculation is proportional.

3. Heteroscedasticity Test

According to Ghazali (2016), the heteroscedasticity test aims to test whether in the model there is an unequal variance of the residuals of another observation. A good regression model is not heteroscedasticity.

Table 4. Heteroscedasticity Test

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	3.192	.901		3.543	.001
	X ₁	-.036	.036	-.125	-1.005	.317
	X ₂	-.011	.034	-.032	-.313	.755
	X ₃	-.036	.038	-.115	-.951	.344

a. Dependent Variable: ABSRES

The visible results show that the parameter coefficient for independent variables is not significant namely communication variables $0.317 > \alpha = 0.05$; competence variable $0.755 > \alpha = 0.05$; variable work discipline $0.344 > \alpha = 0.05$; then it can be concluded that the regression model cannot be heteroscedasticity.

Based on the results of data processing that have been done, then it can be known that the relationship model of the multiple linear regression analysis is seen from the following table:

Table 5. Multiple Linear Regression

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-1.304	1.364		-.956	.341
	X ₁	.375	.054	.423	6.939	.000
	X ₂	.191	.051	.189	3.744	.000
	X ₃	.435	.058	.448	7.552	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Y

The equations of multiple linear regression analysis in this study are as follows:

$$\text{Job Satisfaction} = -1.304 + 0.375 \text{ Communication} + 0.191 \text{ Competence} + 0.435 \text{ Work Discipline}$$

Based on the above equation it can be seen that the value of component a or constant equal to -1.304.

The value of component b₁ or the regression coefficient for the communication variable of 0.375 indicates that the communication variable has a positive effect on job satisfaction which means the higher the communication, job satisfaction will increase and conversely the

lower the communication, the job satisfaction will decrease.

The value of component b₂ or the regression coefficient for the variable competence is 0.191, indicating that the variable competence has a positive effect with the variable of job satisfaction which means more high competence, then job satisfaction will increase work performance and thus increase job satisfaction.

The component value of b₃ or the regression coefficient for variable variance in work discipline is as large as 0.435, indicating that variable variability in work has a positive effect with job satisfaction level which means that the height of the

work discipline is high, job satisfaction level of work will increase and vice versa the lower the work performance.

The significance in the multiple linear regression analysis shows that the value of p value sig or the significance value of the effect between the communication variables on job satisfaction is 0.000 where the value of p value sig or the resulting significance value is <0.05, it can be concluded that the regression of effect between variables the communication of job satisfaction variables in this study was significant. The value of p value sig or the significance value of the effect between the

competence variables on job satisfaction is 0.000 where the p value of sig or the resulting significance value is <0.05, it can be concluded that the regression effect between the competence variables on the variable job satisfaction in this study is significant, while the value of p value sig or the significance value of the effect between the work discipline variables on job satisfaction is 0,000 where the p value of sig or the resulting significance value is <0.05, it can be concluded that the regression of the influence between the work discipline variables on the variable job satisfaction in this study is significant.

Table 6. Coefficient of Determination

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.878 ^a	.772	.765	1.689
a. Predictors: (Constant), X ₃ , X ₂ , X ₁				

The result of the calculation of the coefficient of determination (adjusted R Square) from IBM SPSS Statistics 24.0 for the contribution between communication, competence and work discipline towards job satisfaction variables is 0.765 or 76.5%. This shows that the contribution of the communication, competence and work discipline variables to increase the job satisfaction variable was 0.765 or 76.5%, while the remaining 0.235 or 23.5% was influenced by others not examined in this study.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

CONCLUSION

1. Communication has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction at PT. Tribahtera Srikandi, which means that better communication will have effect on increasing job satisfaction.
2. Competence has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction at PT. Tribahtera Srikandi, which means that high competence will have effect on increasing job satisfaction.
3. Work discipline has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction at PT. Tribahtera Srikandi, which means that high

work discipline will have effect on increasing job satisfaction.

4. Communication, competence and work discipline a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction at PT. Tribahtera Srikandi. The contribution of communication, competence and work discipline variables to increase job satisfaction is 0.765 or 76.5%, while the remaining 0.235 or 23.5% is influenced by other variables not examined in this study.

SUGGESTION

1. To increase the effectiveness of communication at PT. Tribahtera Srikandi, we need to improve harmony in communication between employees. One of them is by intensifying both formal and informal meetings so that you can get to know each other better and grow a sense of openness and harmony with both the workmanship and the employee's limitations.
2. To increase competence in PT. Tribahtera Srikandi can be done by improving the skills, especially technical skills related to broadcasting, conducting training internally by the department leaders or sending employees to participate in training conducted by external parties in accordance

with the training needs analysis required by the company.

3. To improve the work discipline at PT. Tribahtera Srikandi, one of them is by increasing employee obedience to company regulations, giving rewards to obedient employees and fair punishment according to the mistakes of employees who violate company regulations effectively increasing employee compliance with work.

4. Further researchers are advised to conduct research by using other independent variables that have not been examined in this research, such as leadership, training, organizational culture and other variables.

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How to cite this article: Kaban LM, Edward YR. Analysis of the effect of communication, competence and work discipline on job satisfaction at PT. Tribahtera Srikandi. International Journal of Research and Review. 2020; 7(7): 417-424.
